

Influence of Different Glass Fiber Sizings on the Mechanical Properties of Glass Fabric Composites: Report of a Round Robin Test

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ABSTRACT

Composite interface is very important role, however, it is difficult to understand interfacial properties chemically and/or mechanically. To extend knowledge of composite interface will be very helpfull to develop the composite materials, so that SIMS provided the opportunity to exchange the information as Round Robin Tests (RRT). This is the first step of RRT and the first report of results of RRT.

1. Introduction

There are many factors which affect on the mechanical or functional properties of composite materials. The effects of surface treatment on interfacial properties are not clearly understood in spite of many efforts by many researches. It is well known that surface treatment is usually performed by silane coupling agent in glass fiber reinforced plastics. This treatment forms a rigid interface between fiber and resin. The conditions of surface treatment such as type of silane coupling agent, curing temperature, curing time, etc. have so far not been optimized. The studies on the interface should be approached from both chemical and physical sides. Therefore the interfacial phenomena can be clarified by either scientist with a wide knowledge or by cooperation between many scientists.

In most of the studies on mechanical properties of composite materials, there are few considerations of the interface and mentions of surface treatment conditions. The information

on the interface was considered to be secret by many scientists. Different studies on the interface can be hardly compared with each other because of different nature of experiments such as different fibers, matrices and fabrication methods. These studies cannot give some rewards for the efforts in trying to optimize the interface.

In these circumstances the round robin test (RRT) for the interface of composite materials were carried out. This round-robin test was performed by using same materials, and estimated and discussed by each researcher's concept of interface.

2. SIMS

SIMS was established in 1993, as a new promising research organization, expanding from an active local research society of composite materials in the Kansai area in Japan, "Kansai Composite Research Association" (1974-1993).

SIMS consists of professional members from all over Japan and even from abroad in different academic fields such as physics, mechanics, chemistry, electronics, and materials science and engineering of metals, ceramics, polymers and composites.

The aim of SIMS is to establish the interdisciplinary concepts on the structure and the role of solid-solid interfaces / interphases in various kinds of composites such as metal-metal, metal-ceramics, carbon-carbon, carbon-polymer, glass-polymer, polymer-polymer, and to communicate these concepts to the academic and industrial communities for further research and development. Composite interfaces / interphases are studied as an interdisciplinary materials science and engineering problem, ranging from chemistry, physics and mechanics. SIMS provided the opportunity to carry out RRT for interface.

3. Materials

In the round-robin test (RRT), tensile and bending tests were performed using glass woven cloth with different surface treatment and vinylester resin laminates. As a first step of RRT in this paper, modulus and strength were reported from each test. Materials used in this RRT were glass woven cloth (44 strand/2.5 cm (warp) * 34 strand /2.5 cm (weft)), two kinds of silane coupling agents and vinylester resin. Concentration of silane coupling agents was 0.4wt% in epoxy silane, and 0.01wt%, 0.4wt% and 1.0wt% in methacryl silane. To remove physisorbed silane coupling agents methanol washing was carried out in 0.4wt% of methacryl silane coupling agent. Accordingly 5 different surface treatments were performed.

4. Format of Report

The format of the report in this RRT are shown in Fig.1. The first page of this report was cover, the second page was contents, next was introduction, experiments, results, discussion and conclusion. After conclusion, data sheets of all experimental results have to be submitted. The participants of RRT can add some measurements and observations such as SEM observation, AE measurement and so

Fig.1 Format of the report in this RRT.

5. Results and Discussion

Ten affiliations participated in this RRT program, but only seven affiliations have finished testing. Affiliations finished the test are as follows: K.U.L (Katholieke Universiteit Leuven), S.F.I.T (Swiss Federal Institute of Technology), E.P.F.L (Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne), A.N.U (Australian National University), E.M.D (Ecole des Mines de Douai), K.I.T (Kyoto Institute of Technology) and S.I.T (Shonan Institute of Technology).

5-1. Experimental Item

The other experimental items for evaluating fiber / matrix interface except for tensile and bending tests could be freely carried out by each researcher in this RRT program. Evaluation methods of the interfaces, therefore, were different from each researcher. The evaluation methods used in each affiliation are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Experimental item used in each affiliation.

	Tensile test	3-Point bending test	4-Point bending test	ILS	Double notched tensile	Fiber volume fraction	AE measurement	SEM observation	Knee point
K.U.L	○	○				○			
E.P.F.L	○								
A.N.U	○	○							
E.M.D	○	○				○		○	○
K.I.T	○	○					○	○	
S.I.T	○	○							
S.F.I.T			○	○	○			○	

5-2. Fiber Volume Fraction

Measurement of fiber volume fraction was performed by EMD (Ecole des Mines de Douai) and KUL (Katholieke Universiteit Leuven). The results of the measurement were summarised in Table 2. Fiber volume fraction was about 60% for each plate in EMD and about 40% in KUL.

Table 2 Fiber volume fraction of each plate: M0.01(methacryl silane 0.01wt%), M0.4 (methacryl silane 0.4wt%), M1.0(methacryl silane 1.0wt%), MW0.4(methacryl silane 0.4wt% methanol washing) and E0.4(epoxy silane 0.4wt%).

	Fiber volume fraction (%)				
	M0.01	M0.4	M1.0	MW0.4	E0.4
K.U.L	42.4	42.9	40.9	42.7	44.2
E.M.D	62.4	59.8	64.3	62.2	63.5

5-3. Tensile tests

Tensile tests were performed using various specimen geometry in each affiliation as shown in Fig.2. Fig.3 and 4 show the tensile modulus and tensile strength of the woven fabric composites reported from each affiliations. Tensile strength of each specimen depended on surface treatment. However clear tendencies could not be observed. It is considered that the effects of surface treatment on tensile strength was not appered. Although surface treatment was insensitive to tensile strength, it is not clear whether surface treatment affect on fatigue, creep and impact properties. Therefore surface treatment must be one of the factors which should be pay attention to get high tensile strength. These arguments means that tensile strength are also influenced by not only surface treatment conditions but also other factors such as specimen geometry. One of the researcher tried to evaluate glass / resin interface using acoustic emission technique or knee point in initial load-displacement curves of tensile tests.

Thickness : 2mm

Unit : mm

Fig.2 Specimen geometry in each affiliation: (a) K.U.L, (b) E.P.F.L, (c) A.N.U, (d) E.M.D, (e) K.I.T and (f) S.I.T.

Fig.3 Tensile modulus of silane-finished glass fiber/vinylester composites.

Fig.4 Tensile strength of silane-finished glass fiber/vinylester composites.

5-4. Bending tests

Bending tests were also carried out using various specimen geometry in each affiliation as shown in Table 3. Fig.5 and 6 show the bending modulus and bending strength of the woven fabric composites reported from each affiliations. Bending modulus and strength of each specimen depended on surface treatment. But clear tendencies could not be also observed for bending tests.

Table 3 Specimen geometry and span length in each affiliation.

	Thickness (mm)	Width (mm)	Span length (mm)
K.U.L	2	10	64
A.N.U	2	20	64
E.M.D	2	15	32
K.I.T	2	15	32
S.I.T	2	15	32

Fig.5 Bending modulus of silane-finished glass fiber/vinylester composites.

Fig.6 Bending strength of silane-finished glass fiber/vinylester composites.

6. Conclusion

This RRT program was carried out to assess the glass fiber / resin interface of composites materials. The format of the RRT program was purposely kept loose to compare the current consider to the interface of each researchers. It was clear that tensile and bending properties were influenced various factor, and the consideration of each researcher for the interface were also various. We believe that this RRT program will contribute to our research for the interface of composite materials in future.

